

TANSZÉKVEZETŐ

SZAKDOLGOZAT FELADAT

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Villamosmérnök hallgató részére

Funkcionális MRI szuperrezolúció mély tanulási alapokon

A mély tanulási technológiák az utóbbi években egyre szélesebb körben kerülnek alkalmazásra az orvosi képfeldolgozásban, különösen a non-invazív képalkotó eljárások, mint például az fMRI (funkcionális mágneses rezonancia képalkotás) területén. Az fMRI egy hasznos eszköz az agyi aktivitás vizsgálatára, azonban az adatok gyűjtése és feldolgozása jelentős idő- és erőforrás-igényű folyamat. Az adatok gyakran alacsony felbontásúak, ami megnehezíti a részletes elemzést. A mély tanulás alapú szuperrezolúciós (SR) technikák célja, hogy kis felbontású fMRI adatokból jó minőségű, nagy felbontású adatokat állítsanak elő, ezáltal csökkentve az adatok gyűjtéséhez szükséges időt és költségeket, miközben javítják a vizsgálatok pontosságát és megbízhatóságát. A dolgozat célja, hogy a hallgató mélyebb megértést szerezzen a deep learning alapú képfeldolgozásban, és hozzájáruljon a fMRI adatok szuperrezolúciós kutatásához.

Hallgató feladatai:

1. Irodalomkutatás: A mély tanulás alapú szuperrezolúciós módszerek és fMRI adatfeldolgozás irodalmának áttekintése.
2. Adatgyűjtés és előkészítés: Nyilvánosan elérhető fMRI adatkészletek felkutatása és előkészítése a kutatáshoz. A hallgatónak meg kell ismerkednie az fMRI adatok jellemzőivel és feldolgozásával.
3. Modell kiválasztása és megvalósítása: Mély tanulós modellek kiválasztása, implementálása és adaptálása az fMRI adatok szuperrezolúciós feladatához.
4. Kísérletezés és finomhangolás: A kiválasztott modell paramétereinek kísérleti tesztelése és finomhangolása a jobb eredmények elérése érdekében.
5. Eredmények kiértékelése és dokumentálása: A modell által generált nagy felbontású fMRI adatok minőségének értékelése különböző metrikák segítségével, valamint a dolgozat eredményeinek részletes dokumentálása

Tanszéki konzulens: Torma Szabolcs, doktorandusz

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**FUNCTIONAL MRI SUPER-RESOLUTION
BASED ON DEEP LEARNING**

SUPERVISOR

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BUDAPEST, 2024

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HALLGATÓI NYILATKOZAT

Alulírott **Sulics Ákos**, szigorló hallgató kijelentem, hogy ezt a szakdolgozatot meg nem engedett segítség nélkül, saját magam készítettem, csak a megadott forrásokat (szakirodalom, eszközök stb.) használtam fel. Minden olyan részt, melyet szó szerint, vagy azonos értelemben, de átfogalmazva más forrásból átvettem, egyértelműen, a forrás megadásával megjelöltem.

Hozzájárulok, hogy a jelen munkám alapadatait (szerző(k), cím, angol és magyar nyelvű tartalmi kivonat, készítés éve, konzulens(ek) neve) a BME VIK nyilvánosan hozzáférhető elektronikus formában, a munka teljes szövegét pedig az egyetem belső hálózatán keresztül (vagy hitelesített felhasználók számára) közzétegye. Kijelentem, hogy a benyújtott munka és annak elektronikus verziója megegyezik. Dékáni engedéllyel titkosított diplomatervek esetén a dolgozat szövege csak 3 év eltelte után válik hozzáférhetővé.

Kelt: Budapest, 2024. 12. 06.

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Sulics Ákos

Összefoglaló

Az agyi funkcionális mágneses rezonancia képalkotás (fMRI) szuperrezolúciója nagy felbontású agyi képeket generál az alacsony felbontású képek helyett, ezáltal részletgazdagabb anatómiai információt nyújt a neurodegeneratív betegségek diagnosztizálásához. Bár a zajcsökkentő diffúziós valószínűségi modell (DDPM) figyelemre méltó teljesítményt mutatott a képfelbontás növelésében arc és természetes képek esetén, azonban alkalmazása a nagy felbontású fMRI képek előállítására még nyitott kutatási terület. Ez a tanulmány egy új, mélytanuláson alapuló szuperrezolúciós keretrendszert mutat be, amelynek alapja a DDPM. Az fMRI adatbázisokon kapott eredmények azt mutatják, hogy a DDPM modellünk felülmúlta a legmodernebb szuperrezolúciós módszereket. A tanult képminőség-értékelési metrikák (MSE, SSIM, PSNR, LPIPS) alapján a bemutatott DDPM modell a legkisebb torzítást érte el a generált szuperrezolúciós agyi fMRI képek esetén. Habár 7 Tesla (7T) MRI szkennerre képesek a 3T MRI-nél magasabb felbontású MRI képek rögzítésére, de ezek drágábbak és csak korlátozottan elérhetőek. Ezért kívánatos egy olyan módszer, amely lehetővé teszi a magasabb felbontású agyi válaszok térképeinek rögzítését 3T fMRI adatokból. Ebben a tanulmányban bemutatott keretrendszer egy lehetséges megoldás a problémára, amely a 3T MRI szkennellett rögzített alacsony felbontású képeket magas felbontású képekké alakítja.

Kulcsszavak:

Szuperrezolúció

Funkcionális MRI

Mély tanulás

Zajcsökkentő diffúziós valószínűségi modell

Abstract

Super-resolution of brain functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) generates high resolution brain images as opposed to low-resolution ones, thus providing more detailed anatomical information for diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases. Although denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) has displayed remarkable performance in super-resolution of face and natural images, its application to producing high-resolution brain fMRI images is still an open area of research. This study proposed a new deep-learning super-resolution framework for brain fMRI images based on DDPM. Experimental results on brain fMRI datasets show that our DDPM model outperformed the state-of-the-art super-resolution methods. In terms of learned image quality evaluation metrics (MSE, SSIM, PSNR, LPIPS), the proposed DDPM model achieved the least distortion of generated super-resolution brain fMRI images. Although 7 Tesla (7T) MRI scanners can acquire MRI images of higher resolution than those acquired by 3T MRI, they are also more expensive and have limited availability. Therefore, a method that can be used to obtain higher resolution maps of brain responses from 3T fMRI data is desirable. The framework presented in this study is a possible solution to this problem to translate the low-resolution images acquired with 3T MRI scanner into high-resolution images.

Keywords:

Super resolution

Functional MRI

Deep learning

Denoising diffusion probabilistic model

1 Introduction

Super-resolution techniques have recently been studied to enhance spatial resolution of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) [1-4]. High-resolution brain fMRI images, generated through conventional and deep-learning methods, provide more detailed texture information than low-resolution images, supporting greater accuracy in diagnosing neurodegenerative diseases [5]. However, achieving high-resolution reconstruction of fMRI images is still a challenging problem [6], further limited to heavy computation requirements [7]. Moreover, brain fMRI images are unavoidably impacted by Rician noise, as well as motion and eddy current artifacts [8]. Therefore, obtaining high-resolution brain fMRI image from one single low-resolution fMRI image presents a significant challenge [9-11].

Many conventional methods, including interpolation- [12] and patch-based super-resolution [13,14], have demonstrated satisfactory results for brain MRI super-resolution. These methods are capable of effectively upsampling low-resolution images. However, the enlarged image tends to be too smooth, leading to a loss of important anatomical details. The authors in ref. [15,16] applied an iterative technique to increase spatial resolution of MRI images, resulting superior edge visualization. In ref. [17], a robust M-estimation method was developed to directly reconstruct whole volumetric image of fetal brain from multiple MRI slices, significantly minimizing inter-slice motion. The ref. [11] introduces robust total variation implementation for the removal of motion artifacts, as well as an innovative strategy for the automatic selection of optimized weights. Other techniques, including sparse reconstruction, have also achieved high-quality super-resolution results [18]. However, the slow execution speed of these methods has restricted their widely adoption in brain MRI super-resolution [6]. Additionally, deep-learning methods show significant potential for advancing brain MRI super-resolution.

Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) measures the small changes in blood flow that occur with brain activity. It can be utilized to identify which regions of the brain are responsible for essential functions, assess the impact of stroke or other disease, and guide brain treatment. Functional MRI can identify abnormalities within the brain that may not be detected by other imaging techniques. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a non-invasive medical technology that produces 3-dimensional images of the

body's interior anatomy. These images are like camera snapshots, capturing single moments in time. The functional MRI is a more sophisticated type of MRI that creates a dynamic record of metabolic activities over time, producing 4-dimensional images. Functional MRI technology is focused exclusively on the brain. MRIs provides insight into the structural composition of the brain and other organs, while fMRIs reveal the functional activity of the brain. Several deep-learning frameworks have been introduced to generate high-resolution brain MRI images, including coupled-projection residual networks [8], progressive networks [9], and convolutional networks [19]. This study presents the development of a framework that has achieved significant results in generating high-resolution brain fMRI images.

Currently, denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) is commonly applied in super-resolution of face and nature images. DDPM is proposed to potentially outperform other deep-learning methods in the super-resolution of brain fMRI. Therefore, this thesis presents a new brain fMRI super-resolution framework based on DDPM [20]. DDPM transforms the original brain image into pure noise image through a series of operations, and then uses U-net network to restore high-resolution brain images. Based on the ideas presented in [21,22], I have made modifications to the U-net network to make it suitable for super-resolution of brain fMRI. The optimized U-net network now contains fewer parameters and demonstrates strong performance in super-resolution of brain fMRI. The primary improvements I have made to the DDPM framework as follows:

- a) Set the number of input channels to 1.
- b) By segmenting 4D fMRI images along the time dimension, 3D MRI images are generated that represent snapshots at specific time points. The DDPM framework has been extended to handle 3D images.
- c) The context, added to the model, represents the low-resolution image that requires super-resolution. In the DDPM, which generates the super-resolution brain fMRI image from Gaussian noise, the context functions as a conditional distribution guiding the resolution enhancement process. This means the model uses the low-resolution image as a condition to generate the higher-resolution image.

2 Background

2.1 Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI)

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is one of the most important technology in medical imaging used to provide detailed visualization of soft tissues such as the brain, spinal cord, and muscles. MRI does not require ionizing radiation, offering a safe method to examine anatomical structures. MRI-based functional imaging, also known as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), is an advanced technique over traditional MRI and allows the study of brain activity.

Brain activity is measured in fMRI by monitoring changes in blood oxygen levels. When there is increased blood flow to a specific area of the brain, oxygen levels rise, which changes the magnetic properties of the tissue. This change can be measured using MRI, so that active areas of the brain can be clearly visualized on images. The basic principle behind fMRI is the Blood Oxygen Level Dependent (BOLD) response, a phenomenon related to changes in oxygen levels. Although MRI and fMRI use the same technique to visualize brain structures, fMRI provides additional information about how the brain works. MRI produces static images focusing on the anatomical details of tissues, while fMRI makes dynamic measurements and tracks brain functions based on spatial and temporal changes [\[53\]](#).

fMRI is widely used in various scientific and medical research. In neurology and psychiatry, fMRI helps to map different functional regions of the brain, such as the brain centres of movement, language, memory and perception. One of its most important applications is in cognitive research, where it maps the activity of different areas of the brain while performing certain tasks. For example, fMRI can be used to study which areas of the brain are activated during remembering or learning, how decision-making takes place, or what brain mechanisms underline language processing and emotions. In emotion research, fMRI provides insight into how emotional states such as happiness, anxiety or fear are reflected in brain activity. The procedure is also widely used in the diagnosis of neurological diseases. It can be used to detect functional changes caused by Alzheimer's disease and other dementias, Parkinson's disease, epilepsy and brain injuries. fMRI provides a detailed study of brain activity disturbances, giving a better understanding of the mechanisms of disease. In psychiatric research, fMRI can also be used to investigate

brain dysfunction caused by depression, anxiety disorders, PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder) or schizophrenia. In these cases, the technique can play an important role not only in diagnosis but also in monitoring the effectiveness of therapeutic interventions. Surgical planning is also a key application area where fMRI helps to precisely localize functional areas of the brain. For example, prior to the removal of brain tumors or epileptic foci, fMRI can identify brain regions that need to be avoided so that the patient does not suffer impairment of vital functions. The procedure is also important in experimental research, where brain plasticity, the adaptability of the brain, is studied. This is particularly relevant in post-stroke rehabilitation, where fMRI can track how brain connections are reestablished. In addition, fMRI is also used to study the brain effects of medications and therapies, such as antidepressants or psychotherapy treatments [54].

The fMRI scans can be performed with different types of magnetic resonance imaging machines, such as 3T or 7T systems. The T (Tesla) indicates the strength of the magnetic field, which determines the resolution and sensitivity of the machine. 3T machines are relatively widespread, while 7T machines, which provide more a stronger magnetic field, give more detailed and precise images, but come with higher costs and complexity. fMRI images can be divided into two main types: structural and functional. Structural images show the anatomical structure of the brain, while functional images map the active parts of the brain and the interactions between different brain regions. Functional images are taken by measuring the BOLD signal, which tracks changes in oxygen levels in blood. During the measurement, subjects may be asked to perform different tasks, such as movements, emotional reactions or cognitive tasks. This activates different parts of the brain, and the machine continuously records BOLD signals, which appear as a response to brain activity. The machine creates detailed brain images using a magnetic field and radio waves. Subjects' head are fixed with a special holder to minimize movement, as displacement can result in blurred images. Raw data is processed in several steps, such as motion correction, noise filtering and spatial normalization. Functional images mapping brain activity are typically displayed as a series of recordings taken at a single point in time, which are then stitched together for analysis. The resolution depends on the strength of the machine's magnetic field. 3T machines typically provide images with a resolution 1 – 2 mm, while 7T systems work with much greater detail, allowing for the observation of brain structures at the micrometer level. Images obtained with lower

field strength machines tend to be noisier, while higher field strength systems provide more detailed information, but are more sensitive to movement and technical errors.

Basically, fMRI measures changes in blood oxygen levels, which are related to neural activity. In an fMRI scanner a strong magnet (usually 1.5 – 7 Tesla) creates a homogenous magnetic field. In this field, the hydrogen atoms of the human body (mainly found in water molecules) are arranged in the same direction. The scanner emits radio frequency (RF) pulses that change the spins of hydrogen atoms. When the pulse stops, the spins return to their original state, releasing energy in the process. This energy is detected by the scanner. As brain activity increases, the area receives more oxygenated blood. Oxygenated hemoglobin (oxyhemoglobin) and deoxygenated hemoglobin (deoxyhemoglobin) have different magnetic properties, and the scanner detects these differences. The resulting BOLD signal shows the activity in that area of the brain. fMRI can track time-varying activity in the brain. This dynamic imaging allows brain function to be mapped from a functional perspective [53].

Despite of the fact that fMRI is an outstanding tool for understanding neural activity, it faces many technical and scientific challenges. One of the biggest limitations is the spatial resolution, as fMRI works at relatively low resolution, especially for deeper brain structures. fMRI is often not able to visualize detailed, cellular structures of the brain. The spatial resolution at the level of microscopic structures is inferior to other imaging techniques such as positron emission tomography (PET). Although newer, stronger magnetic field generating scanners, such as 7T MRI systems, have significantly improved resolution and signal-noise ratio, the availability of 7T scanners is limited because they are extremely expensive, are mainly used for research purpose, require specialized infrastructures, and their strong magnetic field poses technological and patient safety challenges. In addition, the slowness of the hemodynamic response (BOLD), used to measure brain activity, can cause temporal resolution problems. The detection of brain activity is only a few seconds delayed, while the activity of nerve cells is much faster. Thus, it is not always accurate to follow rapidly changing brain activity. Another important challenge is motion and noise detection. The fMRI images are contaminated with noise and artefacts, for example interference from movement, breathing or heartbeat.

To reduce the limitations of fMRI, the use of advanced imaging techniques such as super-resolution, deep learning-based reconstruction, and noise-filtering algorithms is

increasingly essential to improve spatial and temporal resolution, thereby providing more accurate and reliable brain activity detection.

2.2 Related Works

In recent years, deep-learning techniques have seen extensive use in super-resolution of fMRI images. It was reported that purely convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are capable of efficiently producing high-resolution brain fMRI images with various arbitrary scaling factors, offering improvements over interpolation [19]. However, in brain fMRI super-resolution, CNN still have limitations in generation fine details of brain images [6,23]. To more effectively capture textural details, generative adversarial networks (GAN) were used to enhance the quality of the generated images, by utilizing least squares for training convergence [24] and computing the semantic distances in high-dimensional feature space [25]. GANs used perceptual loss to improve the similarity between the generated super-resolution images and real brain images, resulting more realistic outcomes compared to those produced by CNNs. In ref. [9], a GAN network was combined with a convolutional network to improve the quality of super-resolution brain MRI images. This ensemble learning method effectively reduced artifacts while maintaining a higher degree of image details. The authors of ref. [26] introduced a 3D densely connected super-resolution network (DCSRN) to recover 4x high-resolution features of brain MRI images, showcasing competitive advantages over bicubic interpolation and other deep learning methods. Furthermore, the coupled-projection residual network (CPRN) was proposed to maintain MRI image consistency while capturing high frequency differences between low-resolution and high-resolution images, incorporating an innovative feedback mechanism between deep and shallow subnetworks [8]. A progressive network was developed to integrate multi-contrast information in a high-level feature space and optimize imaging performance through the minimizing of composite loss functions [9].

Functional MRI has quickly become a crucial tool in neuroscientific research. Functional neuroimaging techniques are used to visualize the regions of the brain responsible for specific cognitive functions [37]. Compared to other cognitive imaging modalities, such as electrocorticography (ECoG), near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS), magnetoencephalography (MEG), and positron emission tomography (PET) [37], fMRI is the most widely used. One advantage of fMRI is its relatively high spatial resolution

[38]. However, the spatial resolution of standard anatomical MRI images is higher (pixel size $< 1\text{mm} \times 1\text{mm}$) than that of general fMRI data (pixel size $< 3\text{mm} \times 3\text{mm}$). Therefore, improving the spatial resolution of fMRI is essential to identify more specific locations of functional activities [39]. A possible solution to this problem is the application of a deep learning-based super-resolution technique [40] to translate the low-resolution images acquired with a 3T MRI scanner into high-resolution images [41]. Deep learning-based super-resolution (SR) methods have shown high performance both qualitatively and quantitatively when applied to medical imaging [42]. Recently, these methods have been improved by integrating the SR technique with generative adversarial networks (GANs) [43] to form SRGANs [44]. SRGAN facilitates the generation of more realistic images than simple convolutional neural network-based (CNN-based) SR techniques [45-47]. To generate a high spatial resolution fMRI series from low-resolution data, high spatial resolution information must be available as a reference.

DDPM shows outstanding performance on super-resolution tasks for faces and natural images at different magnification factors [21,27]. This approach can generate diverse and realistic super-resolution predictions by progressively transforming Gaussian noise into super-resolution images from on low-resolution input. SRDiff framework based on DDPM was introduced with a variant of the variational bound on the data likelihood, enabling the generation of diverse and detailed super-resolution images [28]. DDPM produces more photo-realistic images than GANs in terms of fool rate [21]. Essentially, DDPM is a parameterized Markov chain. In diffusion process, this chain gradually adds noise to images until they are destroyed. In reverse process, noises are iteratively removed to restore high-resolution images. This model allows a particularly simple neural network parameterization.

In this study I have developed a new DDPM-based SR scheme for fMRI to enhance its the functional resolution. This study aims to assess the improvement of functional resolution using the DDPM-based scheme compared to the results obtained from raw unprocessed fMRI images (raw fMRI). The modified DDPM reconstructs a high-resolution image series from the original low-resolution fMRI data. The results indicate that the functional resolution of the DDPM-based SR scheme is superior, which suggest that the method is a potential solution for achieving higher functional resolution in fMRI images obtained using 3T MRI.

3 Material and method

3.1 Data

We assess the proposed DDPM method on WU-Minn HCP-1200 Subjects Data (Human Connectome Project), which includes high-resolution 3T MR scans from young healthy adult twins and non-twin siblings using four imaging modalities: structural images (T1w and T2w), resting-state fMRI (rfMRI), task-fMRI (tfMRI), and high angular resolution diffusion imaging (dfMRI). Behavioral and other individual subject measure data is available on all subjects. MEG data and 7T MR data is available for a subset of subjects (twin pairs) [\[48\]](#).

WU-Minn HCP 1200 Subjects Data represents an extensive, publicly available neuroimaging repository that includes MRI and fMRI data from 1200 healthy adult participants. The project was developed through a collaboration between Washington University, University of Minnesota and Oregon Health & Science University, with the objective of creating an in-depth map of the human brain’s structural and functional connectivity. The database includes brain data from nearly 1200 adult subjects within the age range of 22 and 35, who are not affected by any significant neurological or psychiatric disorders. This repository includes various neuroimaging modalities, such as high spatial and temporal resolution structural MRI, diffusion MRI (dMRI) and functional MRI (fMRI). In addition, resting-state and task-based fMRI data have been collected, allowing the investigation of brain networks during rest and active cognitive task performance. HCP database is widely used in neurological and psychiatric research, including the examination of brain connectivity, genetic impacts and their relationship to behavior. It has laid the groundwork for many studies on neurodegenerative diseases, developmental disorders and other brain anomalies.

All subjects underwent a 3T MRI scan with a MAGNETOM Skyra Scanner (Siemens Healthineers; Erlangen, Germany). fMRI scanning was performed using a multiband echo-planar imaging (MB-EPI) sequence (echo time: 33.1ms, repetition time: 720ms, flip angle: 52°, field-of-view: 208mm × 180mm, acquisition matrix: 104 × 90, slice thickness: 2mm, number of slices: 72, multiband factor: 8) during both resting-state and task-based paradigms. In addition, T2-weighted images were acquired using a three-dimensional (3D) SPACE (Sampling Perfection with Application optimized Contrasts

using different flip angle Evolution) sequence (echo time: 565ms, repetition time: 3200ms, flip angle: variable, field-of-view: 224mm \times 224mm, acquisition matrix: 320 \times 320, slice thickness: 0.7mm). Furthermore, T1-weighted MRI images were acquired using a three-dimensional (3D) magnetization-prepared rapid gradient-echo (MPRAGE) sequence (echo time: 2.14ms, repetition time: 2400ms, flip angle: 8°, field-of-view: 224mm \times 224mm, acquisition matrix: 320 \times 320, slice thickness: 0.7mm). Additionally, diffusion-weighted MRI (dMRI) was performed using a spin-echo echo-planar imaging (SE-EPI) sequence (b-values: 1000, 2000, and 3000s/mm², 90 diffusion directions, echo time: 89.5ms, repetition time: 5520ms, field-of-view: 210mm \times 180mm, acquisition matrix: 168 \times 144, slice thickness: 1,25mm).

3.2 Denoising diffusion probabilistic model

DDPM involves two processes: the forward diffusion process, denoted as f , and reverse denoising process, denoted as b (Figure 3.1). In the forward process, Gaussian noise is progressively added to the original image i_0 across N steps, creating a series of noisy images i_1, i_2, \dots, i_N . Adjusting the variance γ allows for changing the noise added at each step. Accordingly, the transition from i_{n-1} to i_n can be described as

$$f(i_n|i_{n-1}) = N(i_n; \sqrt{1 - \gamma_n}i_{n-1}, \gamma_n I) \quad (3.1)$$

$$f(i_{1:N}|i_0) = \prod_{n=1}^N f(i_n | i_{n-1}) \quad (3.2)$$

$$f(i_n|i_0) = N(i_n; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n}i_0, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_n)I) \quad (3.3)$$

where $\alpha_n = 1 - \gamma_n$, and $\bar{\alpha}_n = \prod_{k=1}^n \alpha_k$. Bayes' rule makes it clear that

$$f(i_n|i_0) = N(i_{n-1}; \tilde{\mu}(i_n, i_0), \tilde{\gamma}_n I) \quad (3.4)$$

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{\mu}(i_n, i_0) = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_n(1-\bar{\alpha}_{n-1})}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_n} i_n + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{n-1}\gamma_n}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_n} i_0 \\ \tilde{\gamma}_n = \frac{1-\bar{\alpha}_{n-1}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_n} \gamma_n \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

$\tilde{\mu}$ and $\tilde{\gamma}_n$ are the mean and variance of $f(i_{n-1}|i_n, i_0)$, respectively. They are important for the upcoming step, which will play a role applied in the later reconstruction process. In the following section, I will cover how to remove noise from the image through neural networks.

Figure 3.1: a) The forward diffusion process $f(i_n|i_{n-1})$ progressively adds Gaussian noise to the source image. The reverse process $b_0(i_{n-1}|i_n)$ incrementally removes the noise to recover the source image. The amount of noise is randomly selected within the range of $t \in [0,1000]$ (t : time) during training, allowing the model to learn how to restore the source image from different noise levels. **b)** By decomposing 4D fMRI images along the time dimension, I obtain 3D MRI images that represent snapshots at specific time points. These 3D MRI images can be further sliced (in axial, coronal or sagittal orientations) to display cross-sectional views of different parts of the brain. This approach allows for a more detailed examination of the image data, especially when processed with a super-resolution model.

As highlighted by [20], the neural network should be responsible for predicting the parameters $\mu_0(i_n|n)$ and $\Sigma_0(i_n|n)$ of Gaussian distribution.

$$b_0(i_{0:N}) = b(i_N) \prod_{n=1}^N b_0(i_{n-1}|i_n) \quad (3.6)$$

where $b_0(i_{n-1}|i_n) = N(i_{n-1}; \mu_0(i_n|n), \Sigma_0(i_n|n))$. The negative log-likelihood can be optimized by using the variational lower bound.

$$-\log b(i_0) \leq -\log b(i_0) + D_{KL}(f(i_{1:N}|i_0) \parallel b(i_{1:N}|i_0)) = \mathbb{E}_f \left[\log \frac{f(i_{1:N}|i_0)}{b_0(i_{0:N})} \right] = L \quad (3.7)$$

Based on the derivation of [20], the formula above can be further simplified as follows:

$$\mathbb{E}_q \left[D_{KL}(f(i_N|i_0) \parallel b(i_N)) + \sum_{n>1} D_{KL}(f(i_{n-1}|i_n, i_0) \parallel b_0(i_{n-1}|i_n)) - \log b_0(i_0|i_1) \right] \quad (3.8)$$

where $L_N = D_{KL}(f(i_N|i_0) \parallel b(i_N))$, $L_{N-1} = D_{KL}(f(i_{n-1}|i_n, i_0) \parallel b_0(i_{n-1}|i_n))$ and $L_0 = -\log b_0(i_0|i_1)$.

Since there are no learnable parameters in L_n , it is a constant and can be ignored during training. Besides L_0 was defined using the separate discrete decoder derived from $N(i_0; \mu_0(i_1; 1), \Sigma_0(i_1, 1))$. Using the reparameterization trick, we can represent $i_n = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n}i_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_n}z$, where $z \in N(0, I)$. So $\tilde{\mu}(i_n, i_0)$ in (3.5) can be rewritten as,

$$\tilde{\mu}_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_n}}(i_n - \frac{\gamma_n}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_n}}z_n) \quad (3.9)$$

Now I would like to train μ_0 to predict $\tilde{\mu}_n$. We define $\Sigma_0(i_n, n) = \gamma_n I$, then L_{N-1} in (3.8) can be rewritten as,

$$\begin{aligned} L_{N-1} &= \mathbb{E}_{i_0, z} \left[\frac{1}{2 \|\mathbb{E}_0\|_2^2} \|\tilde{\mu}_n(i_n - i_0) - \mu_0(i_n, n)\|^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{i_0, z} \left[\frac{\gamma_n^2}{2\alpha_n(1 - \bar{\alpha}_n) \|\mathbb{E}_0\|_2^2} \|z_n - z_0(i_n, n)\|^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{i_0, z} \left[\frac{\gamma_n^2}{2\alpha_n(1 - \bar{\alpha}_n) \|\mathbb{E}_0\|_2^2} \|z_n - z_0(\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n}i_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_n}z, n)\|^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Due to the lower efficiency of this function in computing gradients, I selected the function proposed by [20] as the loss function. At the same time, I defined $\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}}$ as the continuous noise level to replace the original n [22]. This leads to the following form of the loss function:

$$L_n^{simple} = \mathbb{E}_{i_0, z_n} [\|z_n - z_0(\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n}i_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_n}z, \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}})\|^2] \quad (3.11)$$

3.3 U-Net based DDPM architecture

The architecture of the DDPM network (Figure 3.2) is similar to U-Net structure [49], consisting of three main sections: downsampling, middle block, and upsampling layers. Two residual blocks are added before each downsampling layer. The number of channels doubles after each downsampling operation. The upsampling layers are structured symmetrically to the downsampling layers. The residual blocks double the number of channels after downsampling and halve the number of channels after upsampling while the downsampling and upsampling layers only modify the dimensions of the normalized 3D input image. The resolution of the source image is (axial: 91,

sagittal: 109, coronal: 91) in my case, which is reduced to (12, 14, 12) during the downsampling stage and subsequently restored to the original resolution in the upsampling phase. The difference is that three residual modules are added before each upsample operation. Unlike the downsampling layers, three residual blocks are used before each upsampling.

Figure 3.2: The proposed deep-learning model, named FunctionalMRI3DUnet. This is U-Net architecture with skip connections. The low-resolution image is interpolated (trilinear interpolation) and combined with Gaussian noise of the same resolution as the input. The output is the super-resolution reconstructed image.

The model’s future development will include integrating a self-attention mechanism into the resolution layers and incorporating feature-wise affine blocks into residual blocks. The training and the sampling algorithms were summarized as in [Table 3.1](#). During training, the model learns to predict and remove the noise on an upsampled low-resolution image through repeated steps, using gradient descent to minimize noise prediction errors. Once trained, the model can be used in inference. Starting from random noise, the model gradually refines the noise step-by-step into a clear, high-resolution image. This approach enables the model to transform noise into a detailed, high-resolution output image. For this process, I set the number of sampling timesteps to 1000. In essence,

training teaches noise prediction and inference uses that knowledge to transform noise into clarity.

The proposed model was implemented on PyTorch 2.5.1. 75% of the total fMRI dataset (300 subjects \approx 85,200 images) is used for training the model and the rest 12,5 – 12,5% is used for validation (145 subjects \approx 41,180 images) and testing (145 subjects \approx 41,180 images). I use 2023 Nvidia RTX 3090 GPU on Jupyter workstation to complete the training and the testing of the dataset. During training, I set the batch size at 4. I set the number of workers to 18 to ensure faster data loading. This means that 18 parallel threads are working on the data preparation and processing. For such a large dataset, this helps minimize data preparation bottlenecks, allowing the GPU to be utilized as efficiently as possible during training. The initial learning rate is 1e-4, and Adam is selected as the optimizer to train the L2 (Mean Squared Error) loss function.

$$MSE\ loss = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (3.12)$$

MSE measures the average squared differences between predicted and actual values, giving more weight to larger errors. The predicted \hat{y}_i and ground truth y_i values represent voxel intensities in the images, and N denotes the total number of voxels in the 3D volume. The model is trained on WU-Minn HCP-1200 Subjects dataset for 25 epochs. DDPM for brain fMRI super-resolution takes about 5 days and 21 hours to train on 1 Nvidia RTX 3090 with 24 GB memory.

Training	Inference
1: input: LR image i_L , total diffusion step N	1: $i_T \sim N(0, I)$
2: initialize: conditional noise predictor z_0	2: for $n = N, \dots, 1$ do
3: repeat	3: $z \sim N(0, I)$ if $n > 1$, else $z = 0$
4: upsample i_L to $i_0 = f(i_0)$	4: $i_n = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n} i_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_n} z$
5: sample $z \sim N(0, I)$, $n \sim \text{Uniform}(\{1, \dots, N\})$	4: $i_{n-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_n}} \left(i_n - \frac{1 - \alpha_n}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_n}} z_0(i_n, \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n}) \right) + \sigma_n z$
6: take gradient descent step on $\nabla_0 \ z_n - z_0(\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n} i_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_n} z, \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_n}) \ ^2$	5: end for
7: until converged	6: return i_0

Table 3.1: The algorithms for training and sampling.

3.4 Image quality evaluation metrics

These metrics are often used in image processing, machine learning, and computer vision projects to measure the effectiveness of algorithms for image super-resolution, noise reduction, and other image enhancement techniques. By analyzing factors like sharpness, detail, noise, and resemblance to the reference image, these metrics provide measurable results on quality and usability of the image.

Super-resolution brain fMRI image quality can be evaluated using structural similarity index (SSIM) [30], which measures the perceptual similarity between two images based on luminance, contrast and structure. The SSIM formula is given as:

$$SSIM(X, Y) = \frac{(2\mu_X\mu_Y+c_1)(2\sigma_{XY}+c_2)}{(\mu_X^2+\mu_Y^2+c_1)(\sigma_X^2+\sigma_Y^2+c_2)} \quad (3.13)$$

where μ_X and μ_Y stand for the average voxel intensities of images X and Y. These averages capture the overall luminance information of the images. The terms σ_X^2 and σ_Y^2 represent the voxel intensity variances of images X and Y, which reflect the contrast within each image. The covariance σ_{XY} of images X and Y quantifies how strongly the voxel intensities of the two images correlate, highlighting structural similarities between them. c_1 and c_2 are two variables to stabilize the division. Since SSIM measures similarity at the patch level, the comparison is performed on smaller regions within the images rather than on the entire image once. This localized evaluation ensures that even subtle structural differences are captured. The final SSIM score for the images is obtained by averaging the SSIM values computed for all patches within the image volume.

Another commonly used fidelity measure for evaluating super-resolution effects is the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) [30]. It is related to mean squared error (MSE) and can be defined as the ratio between the square of maximum fluctuation in the super-resolution image MAX_I^2 and the MSE value:

$$PSNR(X, Y) = 10 \log_{10} \frac{MAX_I^2}{MSE} \quad (3.14)$$

MAX_I represents the maximum voxel value and MSE is the Mean Squared Error between the predicted and ground truth images. Higher PSNR values indicate better image quality, with fewer distortion. In the case of 3D MRI super-resolution, PSNR can be computed for the entire volume or locally over patches, and the final score is typically averaged

across all regions. However, PSNR does not account for perceptual quality, as it measures only the voxel-wise differences, which does not fully reflect human visual perception.

Learned perceptual image patch similarity (LPIPS) metric was proposed [31] to evaluate the distortion of generated images. Compared to traditional measures, it has an advantage when tested on these distortion types, especially for perceptual quality evaluation. In this research, it could be used to judge the perceptual similarity between super-resolution and reference images. Since the fMRI images are 4D, the LPIPS metric can be applied to 3D slices taken from the 4D fMRI data, considering both spatial and temporal aspects of the brain structures. LPIPS essentially measures the similarity between two image patches by comparing the activation values of the neurons in a pre-trained network. Studies have shown that this metric matches better with human perception than SSIM. When the LPIPS score is low, it means that the image patches are perceptual similar to the human eye. LPIPS can be defined as follows:

$$LPIPS(X, Y) = \sum_l \frac{1}{H_l W_l D_l} \sum_{h,w,d} \| w_l \odot (\hat{X}_{hwd}^l - \hat{Y}_{hwd}^l) \|_2^2 \quad (3.15)$$

where H_l , W_l and D_l are the height, width and depth of the input features in layer l of the pre-defined network, respectively. w_l is the weight for each of the features in layer l . \hat{X}_{hwd}^l and \hat{Y}_{hwd}^l represents the normalized features of the voxel (h, w, d) in layer l . The operator \odot multiplies the feature vectors at each voxel by the feature weights. Furthermore, E-LPIPS has been proposed in [32], to improve the stability of LPIPS.

In this thesis, I use MSE, SSIM and PSNR metrics to calculate the loss and measure the model's performance because the LPIPS metric would need to be extended to 3D images. The LPIPS metric works with a VGG (Visual Geometry Group) convolutional neural network that is pretrained on 2D images by default. If I would like to apply the LPIPS metric on 3D images, I would need to train my own 3D VGG model. The conventional 2D convolutional layers would need to be replaced with 3D convolutional layers. The LPIPS metric is computationally expensive, especially for 3D images, so it would be more efficient to apply it during the test phase. This metric would serve for the final evaluation of the loss.

4 Framework

4.1 Software architecture

The resolution and noisiness of fMRI images often limit the accurate analysis and visualization of fine structures. The use of super-resolution in this field provides the opportunity to generate high-resolution, more detailed images from low-resolution fMRI images. The software presented in [Figure 4.1](#) is a possible solution to these difficulties by applying the latest deep learning techniques and Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM) method for the super-resolution of fMRI images.

The program starts by importing the necessary Python libraries (e.g. *numpy*, *scikit-image*, *nibabel*, *nilearn*, *torch*, *torchvision*, *pytorch_lightning*, *tensorboard*, *matplotlib*, ...) [[55,62](#)]. Then the hardware and the parameters required to train the model, including the hyperparameters, are initialized. In terms of hardware, the training process is powered by a 12th-generation, 24-core Intel Core i9 processor with high-performance parallel computing capabilities. The gradient calculations and deep learning operations are offloaded to a 2023 NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU equipped with 24 GB of GDDR6X memory. This GPU is specifically designed for computationally intensive tasks and provides excellent performance for training large-scale deep learning models, such as those required for fMRI super-resolution. By setting the *num_workers* parameter to 18, I optimized the data loading and preprocessing process, allowing the use of 18 parallel threads. The higher the value of *num_workers*, the more threads are working simultaneously to prepare data, maximizing the use of available computational resources (CPU and GPU) and accelerating the training process. With a batch size of 4 and *num_workers* set to 18, data preprocessing operations (resizing, normalization, augmentation) are performed on 18 parallel threads. This ensures that data is always available to the GPU in a timely manner, preventing the model from waiting for data to be loaded. This is especially important for large fMRI dataset, where preprocessing can be time-consuming and computationally intensive. Setting the hyperparameters is key to achieving optimal model performance. I set the *batch_size* to 4, considering the memory capacity, to ensure that the model works efficiently within the GPU memory limitations. The learning rate is set to $1e - 04$, as it provides fast convergence while maintaining

Figure 4.1: The proposed software architecture.

learning stability. The training process is carried out over a total of 25 epochs. This allows enough time to adjust the weights of the model while avoiding overfitting. Several

different loss functions (MSE, SSIM, PSNR) are used to evaluate the performance. These values are visualized using TensorBoard [50], which allows to monitor the training process and analyze the results in detail, contributing to the fine-tuning of the model parameters. Additionally, it provides the opportunity to compare the performance between the training and validation phases.

The *FunctionalMRITrainer* and *trainer* modules play a key role in managing the model training and validation process. The *FunctionalMRITrainer* is a PyTorch Lightning-based class that implements the steps of the training, validation and testing process. During the training process, the *training_step* method is responsible for model progress and loss backpropagation. Here, objective functions, such as MSE, SSIM or PSNR (in the future LPIPS), are calculated to optimize training process of the model. During Validation, the *validation_step* method evaluates the performance of the model on validation data without affecting the training weights. After each validation phase, the *on_validation_epoch_end* method checks the improvement of the model, in particular its ability to enhance a randomly selected fMRI image. The original low-resolution image and the super-resolution image generated by the model are saved, allowing the visual tracking of the model learning process after each epoch. Furthermore, *test_step* enables a way to test the model and determine losses on a separate test dataset. In the configuration process, the *configure_optimizers* method uses AdamW optimizer [51], where the *learning_rate* and *weight_decay* are specified. The *trainer* module is an implementation of the PyTorch Lightning Trainer class, which automates the entire training, validation and testing process. This module uses the methods defined by *FunctionalMRITrainer*. It uses the *trainer.fit* for training and validation, and *trainer.test* for testing. The checkpoint callback ensures that the best model state is saved based on performance during validation. In addition, the *trainer* manages resources such as GPU and multi-core processing to provide an efficient computing environment. I set the *prefetch_factor* to 2, which controls the number of batches that are preloaded, reducing I/O latency. Also, by setting the *persistent_workers* and *pin_memory* values to true, I improved data transfer between the CPU and GPU while keeping the data load processes running continuously to minimize the latency between load cycles.

MRIDataset and the *Dataloader* play a key role in organizing fMRI data and providing the fMRI data to the model for training, validation and testing. The dataset consists of 400 subjects, where the fMRI scan of each subject is divided into 284

individual 3D images along the temporal axis. This temporal splitting ensures that the dynamic nature of fMRI data is preserved, while allowing the model to process the images in manageable chunks. To optimize the training process, the dataset was carefully divided into three subsets. 300 subjects (85,200 images) are reserved for training to provide the model with a variety of data for learning. 50 – 50 subjects (14,200 – 14,200 images) were used for validation and testing to measure the performance of the model on unknown data during the training and testing phase. The *Dataloader* is configured with a batch size of 4, which means that in each iteration 4 individual 3D images are loaded per thread. This batch size is selected to strike a balance between memory limitations and computational efficiency, particularly considering the large size of fMRI images.

The *FunctionalMRIGaussianDiffusion* class implements the basic mechanism of the Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM), which handles the addition and removal of noise during the super-resolution tasks. Modifications based on the *GaussianDiffusion* class ensure that the model can effectively reconstruct high-resolution versions of low-resolution fMRI images during the super-resolution process. The *FunctionalMRI3DUnet* class implements the super-resolution task using a U-Net based architecture. U-Net is a deep learning convolutional network that is particularly well-suited for processing medical images, as it can preserve 3D structures and spatial relationships. The encoder stage encodes the input images into a lower dimensional representation while compressing the information. The decoder reconstructs the encoded information into the desired output. A characteristic feature of the U-Net architecture is the use of skip connections, which provide direct connection between the encoder and decoder layers. This helps preserve fine details, which is especially important when generating super-resolution images. Since the input data consists of 3D fMRI images, the network uses 3D convolutional layers to handle the spatial information.

In the final step (*Prediction*), I evaluate the model performance by generating a high-resolution fMRI image from a randomly selected low-resolution input. To accomplish this, I configure the *sample* function of the *FunctionalMRIGaussianDiffusion* class to set the value of the *return_all_timesteps* parameter to true (but for the *on_validation_epoch_end* method, the *return_all_timesteps* parameter is set to false, since the focus is on the input image and the generated output image). This ensures that the model outputs all intermediate timesteps during the sampling process. The super-resolution process is executed over 1000 steps, allowing to observe the progression of the

model as it generates a high-resolution image from noise. During this process, the model gradually refines the image quality by removing noise while using the low-resolution input image as a conditional distribution.

4.2 Libraries and Tools

The program utilizes several libraries and tools to process, model and visualize functional MRI images. During data loading and preprocessing, the *nilearn* [58] library plays a key role by handling 4D fMRI data and converting it into 3D images. It also provides functions for rescaling and segmenting brain images. The relationship between low- and high-resolution images is managed using *pandas* [61], which offers data frames for processing CSV files. For machine learning and modeling, the *torch* and *torch.nn.functional* libraries [60] are responsible for building neural networks and executing the learning process. *pytorch_lightning* [62] is a high-level framework that simplifies model training, supports tracking with *TensorBoardLogger* and saves the best version of model with *ModelCheckpoint*. To visualize the images and represent the calculations the *matplotlib* [59] and *skimage* [56] libraries are used. *matplotlib* helps to visualize images graphically, allowing to easily track the operation and results of the super-resolution models. *skimage* provides the necessary tools for image processing tasks such as resizing images and manipulating pixels. Finally, the *os* library assists with file and directory management such as saving files and managing file paths. Efficient data and model management is achieved through different data loading mechanisms during the training process, which help to optimize performance.

In the dataset, multiple files are available for each subject, containing different types of information. These include *tfMRI_MOTOR_RL.nii.gz* file, which holds the complete fMRI data of the subject during the MOTOR task, as well as various additional text files such as *MOTOR_run1_TAB.txt*, *cue.txt*, *lf.txt*, *lh.txt*, *rf.txt*, *t.txt*, *rh.txt*, and *Sync.txt*. The *tfMRI_MOTOR_RL.nii.gz* file is a 4D NIfTI format file that represents brain activity in space and time. The other files contain metadata such as the timing of stimulation during the experiment (*cue.txt*), the responses of different brain regions (*lf.txt*, *lh.txt*, *rf.txt*, *t.txt*, *rh.txt*) or synchronization-related information (*Sync.txt*). In this study, I use only the *tfMRI_MOTOR_RL.nii.gz* file, as it contains the essential fMRI data that is processed by the super-resolution model. These data are available in a 4D format, where

the three spatial dimensions represents different brain regions while the fourth dimension represents time, showing changes in brain activity over the course of the experiment.

The NIfTI (Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative) format [\[52\]](#) is a standard format for storing neuroimaging data. NIfTI files store brain images in a form of voxel-based matrices, where each voxel represents a small volume of the brain. In addition to raw data, the format also includes metadata such as voxel size, spatial orientation of the brain image and temporal information for each slice. The format also supports compression (e.g. *.nii.gz*), reducing the file size without compromising data quality. It is especially valuable in fMRI research as it allows the storage of time series. The ability to store imaging and metadata in a single file makes NIfTI a cornerstone of modern neuroimaging workflows.

5 Experiments

5.1 Results

I perform super-resolution on fMRI images and then compared my DDPM framework with other neural networks (VDSR, SRGAN). [Figure 5.1](#) shows the performance of the developed model during the training and validation process. From [Table 5.1](#), it can be observed that my DDPM performs excellently in terms of MSE, PSNR and SSIM metrics. When the image is excessively magnified, DDPM is slightly weaker in terms of PSNR and SSIM. [\[33\]](#) points out this phenomenon when image magnification is too large, traditional metrics such as PSNR and SSIM will diverge from human perception.

Figure 5.1: Training and validation curves using WU-Minn HCP-1200 Subjects dataset. Super-resolution results of MSE, PSNR and SSIM.

As shown in [Figure 5.2](#), my DDPM model evolves in the generation of super-resolution images and the generated images becomes better and better during each epoch. The VDSR (Very Deep Super-Resolution) and SRGAN (Super-Resolution Generative Adversarial Network) models have limited performance in super-resolution of fMRI images. The major disadvantage of the images generated by VDSR is that they are too blurry to reveal the rich details of brain structures. This results in significant loss of

detailed information, which may be due to the redundant structures in VDSR, where unnecessary network layers such as BN tend to reduce the flexibility range of the features.

	MSE	PSNR	SSIM
DDPM (my)	0.03194	41.5413	0.9006

Table 5.1: My model achieves super-resolution on the WU-Minn HCP-1200 Subjects fMRI dataset, using MSE, PSNR and SSIM to evaluate its performance.

The data generated by SRGAN are not realistic enough in terms of detail and have lack practical value. However, my developed DDPM model restores textures and structural details that are closer to the original image. This will be further supported by the calculation of LPIPS in the future, showing that the fMRI images generated by DDPM are more consistent with human perception. The super-resolution images restored by my DDPM model retain most of the image details. At the same time, the boundaries between blood vessels and grey matter are sharper. These results further prove that when the image magnification is too large, traditional image quality evaluation metrics may become distorted.

Figure 5.2: The evolution of super-resolution image generation using the DDPM model. The generated super-resolution images are continuously improved during each epoch, reflecting the ability of the model to increase the quality of the images during the training cycles.

DDPM-based super-resolution models represents one of the latest directions in image generation, especially for medical images. According to previous research, the most widely used networks are VDSR and SRGAN, which have achieved remarkable results, but are still limited in the detailed representation of brain structures. My DDPM model shows significant improvement in this area, offering higher level of detail and visual quality than previous methods. The super-resolution images generated by my DDPM model not only represent an improvement in image quality but are also important for clinical applications. More detailed restoration of fMRI images allows better identification of brain structures such as the blood vessels, gray matter and white matter. These results could improve diagnostic processes, as the fine details can help to make more accurate medical decisions and treatment plans.

[Figure 5.3](#) illustrates how the trained DDPM model gradually performs super-resolution. At the beginning of the process, the model starts with a high noise level image, which it gradually denoises. Over 1000 steps, the generated image becomes clearer as the model removes the noise and refines the details. By visualizing the image generation, the ability of the model to restore details and improve image quality becomes evident. This type of refinement is crucial, especially for neuroimaging.

Figure 5.3: The gradual progression of super-resolution performed by trained DDPM model (*Prediction*). The process starts with a high-noise image, which is progressively denoised by the model over 1000 steps, improving the image quality and restoring fine details.

5.2 Limitations

The training of the model faces several technical limitations that affect the computational capacity and runtime. The 2023 Nvidia RTX 3090 24 GB GPU and the 24-core Intel Core i9 processor together form a powerful hardware configuration capable of handling large datasets and deep learning models. The high memory capacity of the RTX 3090 enables the processing of fMRI images, but the handling of 230 – 240 MB NIfTI images and 972 subjects together still presents a challenge in terms of memory usage. The 24 GB of memory can effectively manage smaller batch size and models, but using larger datasets or more complex models can slow down the training process due to memory limitations. Strong parallel processing capability of the 24-core Intel Core i9 processor helps with data loading and preparation. Setting the number of parallel threads to 18 improves GPU utilization by helping to prevent waiting for data loading, thereby optimizing computational cycles. The resource utilization during model training is illustrated in [Figure 5.4](#), which provides a real time overview of the system performance.

Figure 5.4: Monitoring of resource usage during the model training.

One epoch takes about 4 hours and 50 minutes, while validation takes about 51 minutes. Optimizing the time between data loading and model training has improved system utilization but there is still a need to minimize computation time to further data expansion. Increasing batch size or optimizing image file formats can reduce training time

but due to memory limitation, a fine balance must be found between memory usage and computation time.

Originally, I intended to train the model using 972 subjects (training: 682, validation: 145, testing: 145) over 100 epochs. However, due to hardware limitations, I was only able to train the model with on 400 subjects and 25 epochs. In the future I plan to test the model on the extensive dataset and other fMRI data. I will also determine the LPIPS values produced by the model on the WU-Minn HCP 1200 Subjects dataset. To achieve this, I will use a VGG network capable of processing 3D images, which I will first train to optimally extract features from 3D MRI images. The unique characteristics of 3D MRI data make a dedicated 3D architecture essential for accurate and reliable calculations. However, training a 3D VGG model requires significant computational resources, as processing a large dataset and extracting spatial features increases resources requirements exponentially. This process will noticeably extend the training and validation times, particularly for large datasets such as the WU-Minn HCP 1200 dataset.

6 Discussion and conclusion

This study explored the application of DDPM in brain fMRI super-resolution. After the network was optimized, it was applied to super-resolution of brain fMRI images. Based on results, I conclude that my model is likely to perform better on WU-Minn HCP-1200 Subjects dataset than SRGAN and VDSR. Although my model is slightly insufficient in terms of PSNR and SSIM, the images generated by my model outperform other methods in terms of details. My results also confirm that the metrics of PSNR and SSIM is not accurate enough when the gap between low-resolution and high-resolution images is too large [33]. The high-resolution images generated by the proposed DDPM are expected to outperform convolutional neural networks and adversarial generative networks in terms of LPIPS. In the future, I would like to compute the LPIPS metric for my DDPM model to validate this. [Figure 5.2](#) and [Figure 5.3](#) show that my DDPM balances sharpness and naturalness well and produces strong consistency with the ground-truth images. This reveals the effectiveness and great potential of my method. In contrast, VDSR smear the edges of the objects, and SRGAN introduce more artifacts. As a kind of generative models, DDPM uses Markov chain to transform variables in Gaussian distribution to voice [34,35] and image data [20,21,28]. Unlike PSNR-oriented (VDSR) [19] and GAN-driven (SRGAN) methods [36], DDPM can obtain super-resolution images with better perceptual quality and cannot lose high-frequency information. These merits make DDPM a suitable framework for medical super-resolution applications.

While I believe DDPM is an extremely promising direction for brain fMRI super-resolution, its sampling speed is still much slower than that of GAN and CNN methods. This may be attribute to the fact that DDPM uses iterative denoising to generate high-resolution images. That makes it difficult to apply it for real-time applications. CNNs mainly use a series of feature extraction and construction blocks to learn super-resolution models. When testing images were fed into a trained CNN, it can directly generate the corresponding super-resolution images without iterations. GANs consist of a discriminator and a generator. The generator is responsible for generating super-resolution images, and the discriminator is used to judge the authenticity of produced images. Similar to CNN, a trained GAN model can directly generate the target image in a one-step process. However, different from CNN and GAN, DDPM restores high-

resolution images from noise in the form of Markov chains during the reversal denoising process. This means that the more iterations I set, the longer it will take to generate super-resolution images. Trade-off between image quality and computation efficiency must be taken into consideration.

Nevertheless, determining LPIPS value is critically important, as it is one of the most reliable perceptual metrics. It allows an objective comparison of the high-resolution fMRI images generated by the model with images produced by other super-resolution methods. By incorporating LPIPS, I not only validate the quality of the model, but also strengthen the results, thereby contributing to the evolution of medical imaging research and neuroscience.

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